

IMPACT RESPONSE OF NANOPHASED POLYURETHANE FOAM CORE SANDWICH COMPOSITES

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Abstract

In this study, sandwich panels were fabricated with neat and nanophased foam core and 3-layered plain weave carbon fabric/Sc-15 epoxy composite face sheets. Neat and nanophased foam cores with Nanocor® I-28E nanoclay at a loading of 0.5% and 1% by weight were prepared. Sandwich panels were then fabricated using co-injection resin transfer molding (CIRTM) process. Samples of size 100 X 100 mm were then cut from the panels and subjected to low-velocity impact loading using an instrumented impact test setup. Impact response of the panels was recorded and compared in terms of peak load, absorbed energy. The tested samples were then sectioned for optical and scanning electron microscopy to understand the failure patterns. Samples with nanophased foam sustained higher loads and had lower damage areas as compared with neat counterparts. Nanophased foam cores exhibited brittle fracture.

1 Introduction

Sandwich composites are being increasingly used in aerospace, marine, automotive, transportation and other high technology industries. Helicopter blades, optical benches for space applications, nonferrous ship hulls, Raytheon's Premier I, Lockheed-Martin's X-33, and future tilt rotors by Boeing Defense and Space Group, Helicopter Division are some of the applications [1]. Typically, sandwich constructions for these applications use thin face sheets bonded to honeycomb or foam cores. Main advantage of sandwich construction is its ability to provide increased bending rigidity without significant increase in structural weight. Other benefits of sandwich constructions include excellent thermal insulation, acoustic damping, fire retardation, ease of machining, ease of forming etc.

A major concern that limits the usage of sandwich composites is their susceptibility to damage due to impact loading. There are practical situations like tool drops, runway debris, bird strikes, hailstorms and ballistic loading, which induce considerable damage to the composite structures. Low-velocity impact is considered potentially dangerous mainly because the damage might be left undetected, as the surface may appear to be undamaged. Understanding the causes of the formation of such damages and improving the damage resistance characteristics of composites is very important. In case of sandwich structures low velocity foreign object impact can induce damage to the facings, the core material, and the core-facing interface. Damage initiation thresholds and damage size depend on the properties of the core materials, face sheets, and the relationship between the properties of the cores and those of the facings, size and shape of the structure. Mines et al [2] investigated the perforation behavior of polymeric sandwich composite panels under low velocity impact loading. They have shown that the energy absorbing capabilities of the sandwich panels increased with the velocity of impact. The increase in energy absorption was attributed to an increase in the core crush stress and skin failure stress at high strain rates.

In the recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on improving the properties of polymers and foam materials through the inclusion of small amount of nanoparticles like carbon nanotubes and nanofibers, TiO₂, nanoclay etc to improve the materials properties [3-12]. Nano infused polymeric materials have gained interest due to their unique behavior in mechanical and thermal properties over their neat counterparts. Number of publications can be found on nanoparticle infused polymers where the investigators have reported that nanophased polymer systems exhibit enhanced mechanical and

thermal properties as compared with pure polymer systems [3-5].

Polyurethane (PU) foam consists of closed cellular structures embedded in a continuous matrix. This kind of closed cell geometry is attractive for mechanical and insulating properties [6-8]. Polyurethane foam is widely used as a core material for sandwich structures which are mostly used in aircraft, marine and automobile body structures. If one can improve the properties like mechanical and thermal properties of polyurethane foam, it can further lead to higher bending stiffness and improved mechanical properties in sandwich structures.

There have been a couple of studies reported in open literature on the effect of nanoclay on polymeric foams. Benedicte et al [9] reported the study of Poly (ϵ -caprolactone)/clay nanocomposites prepared by melt intercalation. In their study, they reported that stiffness and thermal stability were increased with clay loading up to 5%. Xia Cao et al [10] used the organoclay to modify the polyurethane and found increase in thermal and mechanical properties like glass transition temperature, compressive strength and moduli. They concluded that the morphology and properties of PU nanocomposites and foams greatly depend on functional groups of the organic modifiers, synthesis procedure, and molecular weight of polyols because of the chemical reaction and physical interactions involved. They also concluded that the presence of clay results in increase in cell density and a reduction of cell size compared to pure PU foam. Polyurethane with higher molecular weight polyol showed improved mechanical properties when 5% organically treated clay was added. On the other hand, opposite effects were observed in nanocomposite foams with highly cross linked structure. Uddin et al [11] infused three different types of nanoparticles, namely, titanium dioxide, carbon nanofiber and carbon nanotube to modify rigid polyurethane foams and studies their static and high strain rate properties. They reported significant improvement in the failure strength and energy absorption in nanophased PU foams. However, the nanoparticles used by Uddin et al [11] are very expensive. On the other hand, nanoclay is widely available and is very cheap. Mohammed et al [12] fabricated polyurethane foams with nanoclay and obtained significant improvement in their thermal, flexural, static and high strain rate properties.

Though there have been some studies in the processing and characterization of nanophased

foams, their usage in the sandwich constructions has been very limited. Mahfuz et al. [4] used TiO_2 nanoparticles in fabricating nanophased polyurethane foams for sandwich construction. They characterized flexural response of the nanophased sandwich and obtained 53% increase in the load carrying capacity over the neat foam sandwich. However, their study has been limited to the evaluation of static properties only.

It is clear from the literature review, to the best knowledge of the authors, that there has been no previous study on the impact response of nanophased sandwich materials. Hence, the objectives in the current research work were to fabricate sandwich composites with foams made using nanoclay and characterize their response to low-velocity impact loading. Accordingly, foams panels were made using 0.5% and 1 % by weight of Nanocor® I-28E nanoclay. For comparison studies neat foam (without nanoclay) panels were also fabricated. Sandwich panels with these three types of cores were fabricated with 3-layered plain weave carbon/SC-15 epoxy laminate face sheets. Samples from these panels were subjected to impact loading at 15, 30 and 45J. Impact damage was characterized through microscopic studies.

2 Experimental

2.1 Synthesis of Nanophased Foam and Fabrication of Sandwich Panel

Polyurethane foam was prepared with two different weight percentages of nanoclay namely 0.5% and 1%. Because of low density of nanoclay, low weight percentages were selected for infusion to avoid the agglomeration of nanoparticles in PU foam. The fabrication of nanophased polyurethane foam was carried out in two steps; the first was the doping of liquid polyurethane with nanoparticles and the second, casting of the foam. The density of the liquid foam (Utah Foam Products) used in this investigation, as specified by the supplier was 240 kg/m^3 . It has two parts. Part A is diphenylmethane diisocyanate and part B is polyol. Mixing ratio of part A and B is 52:48 by weight. Part A was selected for infusion of nanoparticles since it is less reactive and has lower viscosity. Nanocor® I-28E, organically modified clay was first carefully measured along with Part A to have a specific percentage of loading by weight. The mixing was carried out by irradiation with a high intensity ultrasonic horn (Ti-horn, 20 kHz, and 100 W/cm^2) in

open air for 30 min at room temperature as shown in figure 1. In order to avoid temperature rise during sonication, external cooling was employed by submerging the mixing beaker in a cooling bath maintained at 5 °C. After infusion, the modified Part A was mixed with Part B by using a mechanical stirrer at about 2500 rpm. After mixing the part A

Fig. 1. Ultrasonic mixing with external cooling system.

and Part B, the mixture was poured into a rectangular mold and sandwiched (clamped) in a hot press. Hot press temperature was maintained at 38 °C and a load of 2.5KN was applied. After 4-5 hours, mold was taken out from the hot press and demolded to get a polyurethane foam product.

Plain weave carbon fabric was used as the fiber material and SC-15 epoxy resin was selected as the matrix. SC-15 was obtained from Applied Poleramic, Inc. It has two parts, part A (epoxy) and part B (hardener, Alkyl Polyamine). Part A itself is a mixture of three components, namely, Diglycidylether of Bisphenol A, Aliphatic Diglycidylether and epoxy toughener. Sandwich panels were manufactured using co-injection resin transfer molding (CIRTM) process to infuse the resin simultaneously into the fabrics for both the top and bottom face sheets.

For the sandwich fabrication, an aluminum plate was laid on a flat surface. A mold release agent was applied on the surface of the mold and a non-porous teflon layer was placed over the mold to allow easy release of the panel. Then a layer of distribution mesh was laid on the non-porous teflon layer. Three layers of plain weave carbon fabrics were then laid over the distribution mesh to form

bottom face sheet. The polyurethane foam core was then placed on the top of the bottom face sheet fabrics. Three layers of woven carbon fabrics were then laid over the core to form the top face sheet. Another porous teflon layer and a distribution mesh were laid on the top face sheet fabrics. After stacking, the complete assembly was covered with a heat resistant vacuum bag, and two infusion lines (one for top face sheet and the other form the bottom face sheet) and one suction line were installed. The entire assembly was subjected to vacuum to drive away any trapped air by opening the vacuum line while closing the resin infusion line. Premixed quantity of resin was then infused into the assembly by opening the infusion line. Resin was drawn into the assembly by the vacuum. After resin was completely infused, the infusion line were sealed and kept under vacuum for 24 hrs to get the sandwich panel.

2.2 Low-Velocity Impact Testing

All the impact tests in this study were conducted using an instrumented impact drop tower device- DYNATUP Model 8210. DYNATUP is equipped with Impulse data acquisition system, version 3. Impulse, v.3 can acquire 8192 data points. The weight of cross head was maintained at 6.62 kg and it was guided through two smooth guide columns. 100mm x 100mm composite samples were placed between the pneumatic clamps. For each type of laminates, at least three samples were subjected to impact at 15, 30, and 45 J. The data was analyzed in terms of peak load and absorbed energy. The absorbed energy is calculated as the difference of total energy (at the end of the event) and the energy at peak load.

2.3 Microscopy Studies

One sample from each type at each energy level was cut into two halves and scanned using a scanner. Further, the impact region was studied under an optical micrograph to investigate the failure modes of the sample. The fractured surfaces were exposed to the optical microscope, using polarized light. One sample from each set impacted at 30J was observed under scanning electron microscopy to understand the deformation and failure behavior at various magnifications.

3. Results and Discussion

Impact response of sandwich structures with and without nanoclay core was evaluated. Figure 2 illustrates the load and energy versus time plot of representative samples impacted at 15 J. At 15 J, the transient response of the samples showed no sharp drops indicating that the ensuing damage is very small. The indication of damage is qualitatively shown by the change in the slope of rising portion of

Fig. 2. Load and energy versus time response at 15 J

Fig. 3. Load and energy versus time response at 30 J

load-time plots which is realized at load of around 1.5-1.7 kN. At 15J, neat core sandwich had an average peak load of 1.77 kN, whereas the average value was 1.91 kN, 1.82 kN for 0.5% and 1% nanoclay samples. Thus 0.5% nanoclay core sandwich had a higher peak load over neat and 1% nanoclay core sandwich. Both 0.5% and 1% nanoclay core sandwiches exhibited higher peak loads in comparison with the neat core sandwich. The peak load increased with the increase in the impact energy to 30 J and dropped at 45 J. Average

peak load value for sandwich samples at 30J was 2.17, 2.25 and 2.26kN for neat, 0.5% and 1% nanoclay core sandwiches respectively, indicating that both 0.5% and 1% nanoclay core sandwiches showed higher peak load values as compared to neat core sandwich samples. The average peak load at 40

Fig. 4. Load and energy versus time response at 45 J

J showed a lower value when compared with that of samples impacted at 30 J. The peak load value for neat, 0.5% and 1% core samples was 1.91, 2.19 and 2.18 kN. Other impact parameters like deflection at peak load, energy to maximum load, time to maximum load and absorbed energy are functions of the stiffness and damage state of the samples. At 15 J these parameters were dominated by the elastic response which is a function of the sample stiffness. As the neat core samples were more compliant they deflected more than the nanophased core samples. The energy absorbed through the creation of damage was also lower. The energy absorption phenomenon was through elastic response, creation of local dent, and localized core crushing.

Load and energy versus time plots for neat face sheet sandwiches with nanophased cores at 30 and 45J are shown in figures 3 and 4 respectively. It is quite noticeable from the transient response plots that unloading regions showed some oscillations at 30 and 45J. This was due to the breakage of face sheet directly under the impact region. The load and energy versus time curves showed a sharp drop in load and it increased again. The first load drop was due to face sheet failure at the impact region and the failure of foam. Some samples exhibited debonding at the interface between the core and the back face sheet. When such a response happened, there was a second sharp drop in the load-time response. The

energy absorbed at 30 and 45 J was through elastic deformation, indentation at the point of impact, core damage beneath the top face sheet, shear fracture of the core and debonding between the core and the back face sheet. These features became clearer with microscopic examinations of the samples.

For the samples with nanophased cores and neat face sheet sandwiches impacted at 15-45 J optical images of cross sectional view of damage area are shown in figure 5. In all the samples impacted at 15 J, only about 20-30% of the core just below the impact location was damaged by the impactor as seen from the optical micrographs. Though the damage looked similar in all samples, the damage area in foam samples under impacted region was different. In almost all the samples, the face sheet exhibited flexural failure with partial penetration. An interesting mode of foam failure was observed in the micrographs. For the neat core, the

Fig. 5. Optical microscopic images of samples impacted at 15, 30 and 45 J

damage is elliptical in shape whose width is more compared to depth. On the other hand, for 0.5% nanoclay core, the width is slightly reduced but the depth of crushed foam increased while maintaining the elliptical shape. However, for 1% nanoclay core sample, the shape of damaged area was more or less cylindrical. The width and the depth were almost comparable. This type of response of the core was attributed to the fact that foam tends to become brittle with the addition of nanoclay. When such samples were impacted, the ensuing damage tended to be localized. On the other hand, neat foam cores deformed relatively in elastic manner. For the

samples with nanophased cores impacted at 30 J and 45 J, it is noticeable that the damage area was more for neat core sandwich samples when compared to that of 0.5% and 1% nanoclay core sandwich samples. The dark areas (dotted line in optical microscope pictures) show the depth up to which the cells undergo breakage. Again, it is clear that, for neat foam sandwiches, the depth up to which cells undergo breakage was less in comparison with 0.5% and 1% nanoclay foam sandwich samples. The breakage of cells was in the region immediately below the face sheet and more localized for both 0.5% and 1% nanoclay foam sandwiches. However, the affected area was elliptical and wide spread in neat foam sandwich. Moreover, the failure behavior for neat foam sandwich was different from that of 0.5% and 1% nanoclay foam sandwiches.

In case of neat foam sandwich, foam failed in shear mode in addition to crushing. It can be noticed from the micrograph of the neat core that the shearing emanated from the edge of face sheet

Fig. 6. SEM images of sandwiches with a) neat b) 0.5% nanoclay c) 1% nanoclay cores tested at 30 J.

where the impactor had partially penetrated. As was seen in the case of sample loaded at 15 J, there was crushing of core below the partially penetrated face sheet. In order to have better understanding of the deformation and damage mechanisms, samples impacted at 30J were sectioned and observed under scanning electron microscope. As the failure modes were similar for 30 and 45 J samples, only 30 J samples were subjected to scanning electron microscopy. Figure 6 shows the scanning electron micrographs of neat, 0.5% and 1% foam sandwich samples. Samples were looked at different depth location along the line of impact. The first micrograph observed was in the area that depicted cell damage. The next micrograph was from the area below that enclosed by the dotted line, which depicted no damage in optical micrograph. For all sets of samples, it was observed that, when subjected to impact loading, cells were breaking or crushing directly below the top face sheet at impact point. But this behavior is quite different for neat foam sandwich samples. In case of sandwich samples with neat, 0.5% and 1% nanoclay core, neat foam samples underwent breakage of cell at impact loading exactly under the face sheet and then exhibited collapsing of cells, (lower region of the micrograph). The second micrograph taken from the undamaged area shows that the cells are intact. For 0.5% and 1% nanoclay foams, the micrographs indicate that there was no collapsing of cells, instead they broke up to the lower region of damaged area. Further, the region below damage area also showed that some of the cells broke while the remaining cells were intact. This phenomenon proved that the cells in nanoclay infused foams were brittle in nature and they tended to break than collapse. This kind of response was attributed to thicker cell walls in nanophased cores as compared to the neat foam cores. From SEM studies, it was found that infusion of nanoclay lead to the increase in cell wall thickness. Neat foam had a wall thickness of $1.34\mu\text{m}$, whereas, 0.5% and 1% nanoclay reinforced foams had wall thicknesses of $1.90\mu\text{m}$ and $2.06\mu\text{m}$ respectively. This observation of cell structure indicated that by infusing nanoclay cell wall thickness increased and caused the cell size to decrease. It was interpreted here that nanoclay particles resisted/retarded the rising of cells in foam, thereby causing the cell sizes to decrease and hence caused increase in cell density (number of cells per unit area).

4 Conclusions

Low velocity impact tests were carried out on sandwich composites with neat and nanoclay (with 0.5% and 1 % clay loading by weight) cores. The top and bottom face sheets were made of 3 layers of plain weave carbon/epoxy laminates. Three samples of each set were tested under impact loading at 15, 30 and 45 J. Impact response of the samples was recorded and analyzed. Optical and SEM studies were carried out to understand the failure and deformation behavior. Following conclusions were drawn from the study:

- Transient load- time plots give qualitative indications of the state of damage in the sample. Nanoclay infused foam sandwich structures exhibited higher peak loads compared with that of neat foam sandwich structures.
- Damage analyses showed that nanoclay infused foams had smaller damage area than their neat counterparts.
- Scanning electron microscopy study revealed that infusion nanoclay lead to the stronger cell structure compared to that of neat foam. Neat foam samples exhibited collapsing of cells, whereas cells in the nanoclay foams were breaking under impact loading. Response of neat core sandwich samples was relatively elastic while that of nanophased core sandwich samples was brittle.
- Improved impact response of nanophased core sandwich samples was attributed to their increased stiffness as a result of increased cell density and increased cell wall thicknesses.

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